

Overall study design

Title of the study	High-Density Lipoprotein Lipid and Protein Cargo and Cholesterol Efflux Capacity before and after Bariatric Surgery		
Document creation date	05/21/2024	Corresponding Email	andreas.huelsmeier@uzh.ch
Principle investigator	Andreas J Huelsmeier / Laboratory Th Hornemann	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted
Institution	Institute for Clinical Chemistry, University Hospital Zurich, University of Zurich	Clinical	Yes

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	1-phase system	1-phase system	methanol: methyl tert-butyl ether: chloroform, 4:3:3, v:v:v
Derivatization	-	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	Yes
pH adjustment	None		

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium formate, Formic acid	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS1	70000
Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS1	5
Separation type 1	LC	Recording mode of raw data at MS1	Profile mode
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	RP	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	1
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
MS type	Orbitrap	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	17500
MS vendor	Thermo	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	5
Ion source	ESI	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Profile mode
MS Level	MS1, MS2	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
Mass resolution for detected ion at MS1	High resolution		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Solvent blank, Internal standard blank	Type of QC sample	Sample pool

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	No
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Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	No	Raw data upload	Available on request
Are metadata available?	No	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

Un01 / Human / Plasma

Provided information	-	Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Un10 / Human / Plasma

Provided information	-	Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Un100 / Human / Plasma

Provided information	-	Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Un101 / Human / Plasma

Provided information	-	Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Un102 / Human / Plasma

Provided information	-	Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Un103 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un104 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un105 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un106 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un107 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0108 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0109 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un11 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0110 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0111 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0112 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0113 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0114 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0115 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0116 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0117 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0118 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0119 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un12 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Un0120 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Un0121 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Un0122 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Un0123 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Un0124 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Un0125 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0126 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0127 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0128 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0129 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un13 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0130 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0131 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0132 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0133 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0134 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0135 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0136 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0137 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0138 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0139 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un14 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0140 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0141 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0142 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0143 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0144 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0145 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0146 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0147 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0148 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0149 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un15 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0150 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0151 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0152 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0153 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0154 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0155 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0156 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0157 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0158 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0159 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un16 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0160 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0161 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0162 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0163 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0164 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0165 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0166 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0167 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0168 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0169 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un17 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0170 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0171 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0172 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0173 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0174 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0175 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0176 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un0177 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un18 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un19 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un02 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un20 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un21 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un22 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un23 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un24 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un25 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un26 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un27 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un28 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un29 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un03 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un30 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un31 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un32 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un33 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un34 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un35 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un36 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un37 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un38 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un39 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un04 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un40 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un41 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un42 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un43 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un44 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un45 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un46 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un47 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un48 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un49 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un05 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un50 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un51 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un52 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un53 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un54 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un55 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un56 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un57 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un58 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un59 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un06 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un60 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un61 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un62 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un63 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un64 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un65 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un66 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un67 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un068 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un069 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un07 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un070 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un071 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un072 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un073 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un074 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un075 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un076 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un077 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un078 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un079 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un08 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un080 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un081 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un082 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un083 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un084 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un085 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un086 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un087 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un088 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un089 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un09 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un090 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un091 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un092 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un093 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un094 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un095 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un096 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un097 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un098 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

Un099 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 178 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 179 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 180 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 181 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 182 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 183 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 184 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 185 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 186 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 187 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 188 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 189 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 190 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 191 / Human / Plasma

Provided information		Additives	
-		BHT	
Temperature handling original sample		Were samples stored under inert gas?	
Dry ice		No	
Instant sample preparation		Additional preservation methods	
No		No	
Storage temperature		Biobank samples	
-80 °C		No	

AssayID 192 / Human / Plasma

Provided information	-	Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

AssayID 193 / Human / Plasma

Provided information	-	Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

AssayID 194 / Human / Plasma

Provided information	-	Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

AssayID 195 / Human / Plasma

Provided information	-	Additives	BHT
Temperature handling original sample	Dry ice	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Biobank samples	No

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) FA[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FA	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	No
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	No	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

1) FA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
d18:0 (d7)	Fatty acid		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

2) DG[M+NH4]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4]+	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

2) DG[M+NH4]+ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
DAG (31:1) (15:0-18:1) (d7)	Diacylglycerol		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

3) MG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	MG	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

3) MG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No				
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No				
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0				
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Internal standard</th> <th>Endogenous subclass</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>MAG (18:1) (d7)</td> <td>Monoacylglycerol</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Internal standard	Endogenous subclass	MAG (18:1) (d7)	Monoacylglycerol			
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass						
MAG (18:1) (d7)	Monoacylglycerol						
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No				
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quanification were done using MS Excel.				
Type I isotope correction	No						

4) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

4) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
TAG (48:1) (15:0-18:1(d7)-15:0) (d7)	Triacylglycerol		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

5) LPA[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPA	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H] ⁻	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

5) LPA[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPC (18:1) (d7)	Lysophosphatidic acid		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

6) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

6) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPC (18:1) (d7)	Lysophosphatidylcholine		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quanification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

7) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

7) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPE (18:1) (d7)	Lysophosphatidylethanolamine		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

8) LPG[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPG	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H] ⁻	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

8) LPG[M-H]⁻ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PG (31:1) (15:0/18:1) (d7)	Phosphatidylglycerol		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

9) LPI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPI	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

9) LPI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPE (18:1) (d7)	Lysophosphatidylinositol		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quanification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

10) PC[M+HCOO]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M+HCOO]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

10) PC[M+HCOO]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PC (33:1) (15:0/18:1) (d7)	Phosphatidylcholine		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

11) PC[M+H]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

11) PC[M+H]+ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PC (33:1) (15:0/18:1) (d7)	Phosphatidylcholine		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

12) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

12) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PE (33:1) (15:0/18:1) (d7)	Phosphatidylethanolamine		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quanification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

13) PG[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H] ⁻	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

13) PG[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PG (31:1) (15:0/18:1) (d7)	Phosphatidylglycerol		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

14) PI[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

14) PI[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
LPE (18:1) (d7)	Lysophosphatidylinositol		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

15) PS[M-H]- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H]-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

15) PS[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
PS (33:1) (15:0-18:1) (d7)	Phosphatidylserine		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quanification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

16) Cer[M+H]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H]+	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

16) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
Cer (d30:0) (d18:0/12:0)	dihydro-Ceramide		
Cer (d30:1) (d18:1/12:0)	Ceramide		
Cer (m30:0) (m18:0/12:0)	1-deoxy-dihydro-Ceramide		
Cer (m30:1) (m18:1/12:0)	1-deoxy-Ceramide		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

17) GM1[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	GM1	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

17) GM1[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
SM (36:1) (18:1/18:1) (d9)	Glycosyl-Ceramide		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

18) Hex2Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Hex2Cer	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

18) Hex2Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
SM (36:1) (18:1/18:1) (d9)	Glycosyl-Ceramide		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quanification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

19) Hex3Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Hex3Cer	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

19) Hex3Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
SM (36:1) (18:1/18:1) (d9)	Glycosyl-Ceramide		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

20) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	HexCer	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

20) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
SM (36:1) (18:1/18:1) (d9)	Glycosyl-Ceramide		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

21) SPB[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SPB	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

21) SPB[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
d18:1 (d7)	Sphingoid base		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quanification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

22) SPBP[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SPBP	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

22) SPBP[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
d18:1P (d7)	S1P		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

23) SHexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SHexCer	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

23) SHexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
SM (36:1) (18:1/18:1) (d9)	Glycosyl-Ceramide		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

24) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

24) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
SM (36:1) (18:1/18:1) (d9)	Sphingomyelin		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quanification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

25) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CE	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

25) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
CE (18:1) (d7)	Cholesterolester		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		

26) AcCa[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	AcCa	Limit of detection	No
MS Level for identification	MS1	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	No
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Isotope correction at MS1	No	Lipid Identification Software	Tracefinder
MS1 verified by standard	Yes	Data manipulation	Smoothing
Background check at MS1	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-
Check isomer overlap	No		

26) AcCa[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
MS Level for quantification	MS1	Normalization to reference	No
Internal lipid standard(s) MS1		Lipid Quantification Software	Tracefinder 4.0
Internal standard	Endogenous subclass		
d18:1 (d7)	Acyl-Carnitine		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Peak picking and integration was done with Tracefinder. Calculations for quantification were done using MS Excel.
Type I isotope correction	No		